

**ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЕ ИКОНИЧЕСКОЙ ПАРЕМИИ
В ОРИГИНАЛЬНОМ И ПЕРЕВОДНОМ ТЕКСТАХ
(НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ДИСКУРСА В. ШУКШИНА) /
THE FUNCTIONING OF ICONIC PAREMIOLOGY
IN ORIGINAL AND TRANSLATED TEXTS
(BASED ON THE LITERARY DISCOURSE OF V. SHUKSHIN)**

Irina CILOCI, PhD Student

(“Alecu Russo” Balti State University, Republic of Moldova)

irusik_2005_89@mail.ru

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0994-0529>

Received: June 1, 2025 | Reviewed: June 3, 2025 | Accepted: June 5, 2025

UDC 81 | DOI from Zenodo

The research focuses on the functioning of iconic paroemia in the original and translated texts (on the basis of V. Shukshin’s fictional discourse). V. Shukshin’s creative activity has become the scope of the study of both Russian and a lot of foreign researchers as in the writer’s literary works the author’s and characters’ voices are uniquely individual. In certain instances occasional paroemia is used in the author’s fictional discourse, which is certain to impede the correlation of such phrases into the Romanian language within the limits of the equivalency of the common linguistic units of the Russian and Romanian phraseological stock. Upon analyzing phraseologisms, we conclude that their equivalents are exact on the semantic level and less frequently precise on the lexical one, which proves the crucial significance of iconic paroemia not only within the language system, but also within fictional discourse.